

Research Article

**Starch Hydrolysis by *RHIZOBIUM JAPONICUM* Species from
Different Soybean Varieties**

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ABSTRACT

Rhizobium japonicum species were isolated from different varieties of soybean. The amylase production ability of each species was detected on modified YMA medium with the substitution of the mannitol by starch. Submerged fermentation was done for the amylase production. Amylase activity was determined by measuring reducing sugar formed by the enzymatic hydrolysis of starch. One enzyme unit (U) was defined as the amount of enzyme that released one μmol of reducing sugar $\text{ml}^{-1} \text{min}^{-1}$, with D-glucose as the standard; under the standard assay conditions. JS 335 soybean variety isolate formed increased reducing sugar as compared to remaining soybean variety isolates. 228soybean variety isolate formed the less reducing sugar as compared to remaining soybean variety isolates. JS 335 soybean variety isolate formed the maximum amylase units whereas DS 228 soybean variety isolate formed the least amylase units.

KEY WORDS: *Rhizobium japonicum*, soybean varieties, amylase and submerged fermentation

INTRODUCTION:

Soybean constitutes a very nutritious food being very rich in proteins. Soybean oil is industrially used in manufacture of paints, oil cloth, printing ink, insecticides and disinfectants. Soybean milk extracted from seeds is used for cooking and is also prescribed for infants. Soybean also has different amino acids. The demand for soybean is increasing. Therefore efforts must be taken to increase the yield. Use of Soybean oil can reduce the heart problem, as it has low cholesterol content.

Rhizobium is a type of bacterium that lives in soil and around and inside of the roots of certain plants (legumes). *Rhizobium* spp. are well known group of bacteria that acts as the primary symbiotic fixer of nitrogen. These bacteria infect the roots of leguminous plants, leading to the formation of lumps or nodules where the nitrogen fixation takes place. The bacterium's enzyme system supplies a constant source of reduced nitrogen to the host plant and the plant furnishes nutrients and energy for the activities of the

bacterium. This symbiosis reduces the requirements for nitrogenous fertilizers during the growth of leguminous crops. This *Rhizobium* in its free-living state in soil, surrounded by a halo of protective covering called a capsule.

The slimy capsule, made of exopolysaccharide, protects *Rhizobium* from drying out. It also helps the bacterium stick to root hairs during other stages of its life cycle, when *Rhizobium* forms a symbiotic partnership with plants. *R. japonicum* forms root nodules on the roots of Soybean. These microorganisms fix the chemically locked atmospheric nitrogen in root nodules and provide to the plants.

Rhizobia were gram-negative, nonperforming, rod shaped bacteria. The cells from late-log-phase to stationary-phase YEM cultures of fast growers tended to become enlarged and exhibited marked pleomorphism.

The symbiosis between the root-nodule bacteria of the genus *Rhizobium* and legumes results in the fixation of atmospheric nitrogen in root-nodules. This symbiotic relationship is of special significance to legume husbandry as seed inoculation with effective strains of *Rhizobium* can meet the nitrogen requirements of the legume to achieve increased yields.

Rhizobium strains can produce amylase and cellulase [4]. Amylolytic enzymes from numerous sources degrade starch, the primary storage polysaccharide in plants. Amylases are among the most important enzymes and are of great significance in present-day biotechnology, having approximately 25% of the enzyme market. New amylases could be potentially useful in the pharmaceutical and fine-chemical industries if enzymes with suitable properties could be identified.

With the advent of new frontiers in biotechnology, the spectrum of amylase applications has expanded into many other fields, such as clinical, medicinal and analytical chemistry. The amylases can be derived from several sources, such as plants, animals and

microorganisms. Because of their short growth period, the enzymes from microbial sources generally meet industrial demands. The first enzyme produced industrially was an amylase from a fungal source in 1894, which was used for the treatment of digestive disorders.. Nevertheless, various other sources of microbial amylases are being investigated in all world. *Rhizobia* strains as promising sources of amylase for biotechnological applications, especially in starch industry [2].

Amylases are among most important enzymes used in biotechnology in processes involving starch hydrolysis [8].

In the present study, The different species of *Rhizobium* isolated from soybean root nodules are tested to produce the amylase enzymes. The amylase units are calculated in $\mu\text{m/ml/min}$.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Amylases are among most important enzymes used in biotechnology in processes involving starch hydrolysis. For isolation of *Rhizobium japonicum*, five soybean varieties as JS 335, JS 71-5, JS 93-05, DS 228 and JS162 were selected.

1) Isolation of *Rhizobium japonicum*:

For Isolation of *Rhizobium japonicum*, seeds of five soybean varieties as JS 335, JS 71-5, JS 93-05, DS 228 and JS162 were selected. These seeds were collected from the various farmers. Seeds were sown in earthen pots using soil from the garden of the college. Three pots were maintained for each variety. The pots were watered regularly and each pot was maintained with at least 5 plants[7].

After 60 days nodules with pink or red-stained tissues were taken from the root system of the host plants. The nodules were surface-sterilized with 95% alcohol for 10 seconds, followed by a surface-sterilized with 1% NaOCl for 4 min and washed several times with sterile water. The nodule contents were streaked on yeast extract-

mannitol agar (YEMA) medium and incubated at 28°C in the dark.

The medium contained (g L⁻¹): 10.0 mannitol, 0.4 K₂HPO₄, 0.1 K₂HPO₄, 0.2 MgSO₄·7 H₂O, 0.1 NaCl, 0.4 yeast extract and 15 agar adjusted to pH 6.8. The isolates were purified through the repeated plating method on YMA. Bacteria from single colonies were then screened for amylase production on modified YMA. [2]

2) Differentiation and Identification of *Rhizobium Spp.* From *Agrobacterium Spp.*:

For the differentiation and identification of *Rhizobium* spp. from *Agrobacterium Spp* the following tests were used [6]:CRYEMA Test, Microscopic Observations, Glucose peptone agar test (GPA Test), Salt tolerance test and lactose test.

3) Amylase screening and production procedures:

Modified YMA medium with the substitution of the mannitol by starch was used to detect amylolytic activity in all *Rhizobium* strains. The plates were inoculated by transferring cells from colonies (5–7 days–old) with a flame sterilized platinum loop and were incubated for 4 days at 28°C in the dark. After cell growth, the petri dishes were flooded with an iodine tincture solution. A yellow zone around the colony in an otherwise blue medium indicated starch–degrading activity. The level of enzyme production was evaluated by the diameter of cleared zone (DCZ), measured in centimeters, on the reverse of the petridishes.

The *Rhizobium* strains selected were investigated for production of amylases in modified yeast extract mannitol (YM) broth medium. YM broth was used as a control [1].

The flasks were kept on rotary shaker for the submerged fermentation at 200 rpm and (30 ±

1)°C, for 48 hrs, with the cells in the final of exponential growth phase.

Starch on hydrolysis yields lower molecular weight polysaccharides and finally to glucose or maltose Maltose is a disaccharide composed of two glucose units. Maltose is a reducing sugar [5].

4) Rhizobial biomass and amylase activity assay:

At the end of cellular growth in each culture medium, the biomass production (g L⁻¹) was determined as cell dry weight after centrifugation (12.000 rpm, 10 min) of the culture medium in triplicate, and dried at 105°C overnight until constant weight.

Analytical procedures and statistical analysis

Amylase activity was determined by measuring the reducing sugar formed by the enzymatic hydrolysis of starch using dinitro salicylic acid (DNSA) method. Reaction mixture contained 2.5ml Acetate buffer (pH 5.0), 2.5ml starch (1%) and 1ml NaCl (1%) in test.

Instead of starch, 2.5ml distilled water was added in blank. The mixtures were incubated at 37°C for 30 minutes. After incubation 1ml of distilled water and 0.5ml of crude enzyme were added to text mixtures and 0.5ml of distilled water instead of enzyme was added to blank.

The mixtures were incubated at 37°C for 30 minutes. Immediately, after incubation, 1ml reaction mixture was added to 1 ml of DNSA reagent. The solutions were kept in boiling water bath for 10 minutes followed by addition of 5 ml distilled water.

The absorbance was measured at 530 nm on spectrophotometer. One enzyme unit (U) was calculated as reducing sugar released per minute per milliliter of the reaction mixture [9] with D–glucose as the standard, under the standard assay conditions described above. [3]

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

1) Isolation of *Rhizobium japonicum*:

After 60 days of sowing, *Rhizobium* cells were isolated from the the nodules developed on the roots. The colonies obtained were large, white translucent, glistening, gummy and elevated with entire margin. The size of the colony was of 1.5mm in diameter.

Photoplate I

JS 335

JS 71-5

JS162

Root nodules on the root

Photoplate II

JS 335

17-5

Screening of amylase activity of *R.japonicum* from different soybean varieties

The nodulation study was as per the method used by [7] in the nodulation study of *Rhizobium* isolated from *Indigofera species*.

2) Differentiation and Identification of *Rhizobium Spp.* From *Agrobacterium Spp.*:

From CRYEMA test, Microscopic Observations, Glucose peptone agar test (GPA Test) Salt tolerance test and Lactose test. *R japonicum* colonies were differentiated and Identified from *Agrobacterium Spp.* *R japonicum* colonies were white, circular and raised colonies The cells showed the stained PHB (poly β -hydroxybutyrate) granules when stained with carbol fuschin.

Rhizobium is unable to grow on GPA medium, on the YEMA medium containing 2% NaCl, unable to grow on lactose agar. These tests confirms that the isolated colonies were of *Rhizobium* species.

2) Amylase screening procedures:

Amylolytic activity on modified YMA medium was tested. Amylolytic activity with a clear zone was measured. [2]

Photoplate III

Starch Hydrolysis by *RHIZOBIUM JAPONICUM* Species from Different Soybean Varieties

JS 335

JS 71-5

DS 228

Isolation of *Rhizobium japonicum* from different varieties

Table 1: Measurement of amylolytic activity

SN	Soybean Variety	Line of Streak in cm		Clear zone in cm.		(Clear zone-Line of streak) in cm	
		Length	Breadth	Length	Breadth	Length	Breadth
1	JS 335	3.6	3.5	4.7	4.3	1.1	0.8
2	JS 71-5	3.2	2.1	4.4	3.3	1.2	1.2
3	JS 93-05	2.5	1.9	2.9	3.5	0.4	1.6
4	DS 228	2.5	2.1	3.4	2.9	0.9	0.8
5	JS162	2.5	2.5	3.8	3.6	1.1	1.1

The zone of clearance was recorded in mm as in the table. The JS 335 soybean variety *Rhizobium* isolate showed the maximum clear zone whereas DS 228 soybean variety *Rhizobium* isolate showed the minimum clear zone. [2]in 2007 checked the amylolytic activity of bacterial isolates obtained from cowpea and soybean root nodules on modified YMA medium. Modified YMA medium was with the substitution of the mannitol by starch and was used to detect amylolytic activity in all *Rhizobium* strains.

4) **Rhizobial biomass and amylase activity assay:** The biomass was measured in the dry weight form in grams. The dry weight was noted down as in the table. The highest dry weight was noted in case of JS 335 variety isolate. The lowest dry weight was noted in case of DS 228 variety isolate.

Table 2: Rhizobial dry weight measurement

Soybean Variety	Weight of whatmann filter paper in grams		Dry Weight of <i>Rhizobium</i> cells in grams/lit.
	Before filtration	After filtration	
JS 335	0.82	1.09	0.27
JS 71-5	0.74	0.88	0.14
JS 93-05	0.73	0.77	0.04
DS 228	0.76	0.78	0.02
JS162	0.73	0.79	0.06

Table 3: Amylase activity assay

S/N	Soybean Variety	Optical density at 530 nm	Concentration of reducing sugar released (mg/ml)	Amylase units formed (µm/ml/min)
1	JS 335	0.170	2.1	0.3889
2	JS 71-5	0.155	1.875	0.3472
3	JS 93-05	0.139	1.700	0.3148
4	DS 228	0.133	1.625	0.3009
5	JS162	0.154	1.850	0.3426

$$\text{Enzyme units} = \frac{X \times 1000}{180 \times 30}$$

X= Concentration of reducing sugar released (mg/ml)

JS 335 soybean variety isolate formed the maximum amylase units whereas DS 228 soybean variety isolate formed the least amylase units.

In the production and optimization of amylase from *Aeromonas jandaei*[8] used the same above method. In the standardization of pH, they used 1% starch in the reaction mixture. The DNSA

method was referred by them for amylase units calculation. The dry mass was measured as per the method of [2]. At the end of cellular growth in each culture medium (3 and 5–days for fast and slow–growing strains), the biomass production (g L^{-1}) was determined by them as cell dry weight after centrifugation (12.000 rpm, 10 min)[9]

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